

Kinetics of Reactions of 2-Mercaptopyrimidines with Allyl Chloride and Benzyl Chloride in Ethanol

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Manuscript received 29 October 1973; accepted 29 March 1974

The kinetics of reactions involving *S*-substitution of 2-mercaptopyrimidines by allyl and benzyl groups have been studied at four different temperatures and the reactions have been found to be second order. Specific reaction rates and other thermodynamic parameters have been calculated. The plot of ΔH^\ddagger against ΔS^\ddagger affords a linear relationship between the two parameters and from it the isokinetic temperature (β) has been computed. The mechanism is proposed to be a direct electrophilic attack by allyl and benzyl group on sulphur.

THE formation of *S*-substituted derivatives of thiourea is well known. The 2-mercaptopyrimidines (Ia-I_f) also behave like thioureas and form corresponding *S*-substituted derivatives. The formation of these derivatives has been studied kinetically in absolute alcohol and is reported herein.

- a, R = ethyl
- b, R = H
- c, R = *p*-methoxyphenyl
- d, R = phenyl
- e, R = *p*-nitrophenyl
- f, R = *n*-butyl

Fig. 1

Experimental

All the 2-mercaptopyrimidines were prepared by the method of Mathes¹ and purified by recrystallisation from suitable solvents. Benzyl chloride (BDH) was purified by distillation at 63° under 8 mm pressure.² Allyl chloride was purified by distillation under atmospheric pressure. Absolute ethanol was prepared from commercial rectified alcohol by the method of Vogel.³ The rate of the reaction was followed by the measurement of conductivity. Common thermostat equipped with a mechanical stirrer, a toluene regulator and an electronic relay was used. The temperatures were maintained within $\pm 0.05^\circ$. Equimolar solutions (*M*/30 or *M*/45) of each of 2-mercaptopyrimidine and allyl chloride/benzyl chloride were thermostated separately, and then mixed and allowed to react in a closed conductivity cell immersed in the thermostat. Resistance was measured at different time intervals with a Philips PR 9500 Bridge. After taking a set of 15-20 readings the temperature of the thermostat was

raised to about 60° to ensure faster completion of reaction. After 20-24 hrs the temperature was readjusted to the original value and the infinite reading was recorded. The reaction rates were calculated by the method described by Frost and Pearson.⁴

After the infinite reading the reaction mixture in each case was estimated for chloride ion by Volhard method, and it afforded satisfactory analyses for complete hydrochloride formation.

The final products of the reactions were prepared separately by refluxing equimolar amounts (2.5*m*. mole) of each of 2-mercaptopyrimidines (Ia-I_f) and allyl chloride/benzyl chloride in absolute alcohol (20-30 ml) for 2 hrs, followed by removal of solvent to 2-4 ml when the hydrochloride derivatives separated on cooling. The m.p.s. are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1

M. P. AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF SOME REPRESENTATIVE ALLYL AND BENZYL DERIVATIVES* OF 2-MERCAPTOPYRIMIDINES (IA-IF).

S. No.	Derivative	m.p. °C	%Cl	
			Calcd	Found
1.	S-allyl-Ia-hydrochloride	138	13.63	13.09
2.	S-allyl-Ic-hydrochloride	184	10.49	10.18
3.	S-allyl-Id-hydrochloride	200	11.51	10.94
4.	S-benzyl-Ia-hydrochloride	128	11.11	10.67
5.	S-benzyl-Ic-hydrochloride	150	9.14	8.87
6.	S-benzyl-Id-hydrochloride	149	9.90	9.50
7.	S-benzyl-Ie-hydrochloride	145	8.80	8.54
8.	S-benzyl-If-hydrochloride	133	10.49	9.97

*Recrystallised from acetone-alcohol.

**The m.p. are uncorrected.

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Results and Discussion

The reaction has been observed to obey second order rate law. The rate is first order in 2-mercaptopyrimidine as well as in allyl/benzyl chloride. Tables 2 and 3 record the second order rate constants at 40°, 45°, 50° and 55°. The values are averages of two or more runs and are correct to $\pm 2\%$. The activation parameters for these reactions are also tabulated in Tables 2 and 3. The values of ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger are calculated for 50°.

From Tables 2 and 3 it is seen that the values of frequency factor increase with increasing energy of activation. So a straight line was fitted between $\log PZ$ and $1/\sqrt{E}$ values. A linear plot was obtained justifying Fairclough-Hinshelwood relationship⁵.

The enthalpy of activation was plotted against entropy of activation and a linear relationship was obtained. So that the correlation⁶

$$\Delta H^\ddagger = \Delta H_0^\ddagger + \beta \Delta S^\ddagger$$

holds good. The value of ΔH_0^\ddagger in this equation corresponds to $\Delta S^\ddagger = 0$, and its value along with β is reported in the respective tables of kinetic data for the two series. The constant β which is calculated from the slope of the line, is called the isokinetic temperature. At this temperature, if the above equation is true, the rate of reaction would be same for all the derivatives in the respective series.

The linear nature of the plot between ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger implies that the same mechanism (at least insofar as the main details are concerned) operates in the whole series.

TABLE 2. SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANTS AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR THE REACTION OF 2-MERCAPTOPYRIMIDINE WITH ALLYL CHLORIDE

S. No.	Compound	$10^3k/1. \text{ mole}^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1}$				E_a kcal/mole	ΔH^\ddagger kcal/mole	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ e.u.	log PZ
		40°	45°	50°	55°				
1.	Ia	2.193	3.133	4.487	6.325	14.29	13.66	27.18	7.316
2.	Ib	1.578	2.296	3.267	4.690	14.58	13.95	26.88	7.380
3.	Ic	1.410	2.070	3.021	4.400	15.14	14.51	25.33	7.720
4.	Id	1.153	1.770	2.634	3.912	16.28	15.65	22.05	8.436
5.	Ie	1.046	1.596	2.458	3.664	16.81	16.18	20.59	8.755
6.	If	0.928	1.432	2.208	3.344	17.33	16.70	19.17	9.065
		$\beta = 354.2^\circ\text{K}$		$\Delta H_0^\ddagger = 23.47 \text{ kcal/mole}$					

TABLE 3. SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANTS AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR THE REACTION OF 2-MERCAPTOPYRIMIDINES WITH BENZYL CHLORIDE

S. No.	Compound	$10^3k/1. \text{ mole}^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1}$				E_a kcal/mole	ΔH^\ddagger kcal/mole	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ e.u.	log PZ
		40°	45°	50°	55°				
1.	Ia	2.482	3.649	5.352	7.724	15.30	14.67	23.70	8.076
2.	Ib	2.328	3.443	5.174	7.475	15.79	15.16	22.27	8.389
3.	Ic	2.188	3.274	4.962	7.271	16.26	15.63	20.90	8.688
4.	Id	1.985	3.055	4.731	7.079	17.19	16.56	18.11	9.298
5.	Ie	1.757	2.713	4.217	6.342	17.33	16.70	17.90	9.344
6.	If	1.716	2.561	3.773	5.531	15.85	15.22	22.67	8.301
		$\beta = 342^\circ\text{K}$		$\Delta H_0^\ddagger = 22.78 \text{ kcal/mole}$					

Fig. 2.

The large negative entropy of activation is as expected for bimolecular reactions with highly polar transition state.⁷ The frequency factors are also consistent with a bimolecular mechanism.

Mechanism of reaction: The kinetic and thermodynamic data are consistent with a second order bimolecular mechanism. The following mechanism is suggested and it involves a direct electrophilic sulphur atom.

It is supported by the observation that electron-releasing groups enhance the reaction and electron-withdrawing substituents decrease the rate. *n*-Butyl derivative is slow to react possibly due to steric hindrance to the approach of substituting group. Phenyl substituents also cause steric hindrance

although they are more effective electron donating groups.

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